

Impact of Selected Demographic Variable on Attitude to Mobile Technology of Teachers working in Higher Education Institution

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to find out the attitude of the teachers to mobile technology working in higher education institutions. 200 teachers from 20 higher education institutions of Pilibhit District, affiliated to Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, were selected randomly as making a representative sample by employing stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire was constructed to collect data followed by survey method and analysed with mean, SD, t-test and p-value statistics. Findings of the study revealed that there was significant difference in attitudes of male and female teachers; married and unmarried teachers and teachers of Government/Aided and Self-finance institutions.

Keywords: Attitude, Mobile Technology, Teacher.

Introduction

In the recent years, a new concept is emerging in the field of Information and Communication Technology which has influenced whole education system and paves a path for smooth digital learning which generally known as Mobile Technology. Mobile technology is in its childhood age in teaching-learning process which is drawing the attention of education stakeholders to its utility in teaching-learning process. As world is moving from manual to digital, so it is necessary that education should also follow the same to meet its objectives. Generally, mobile technology is a cellular technology that makes the use of wireless devices such as mobile devices, tablets, etc. As far as education is concerned uses of mobile devices in teaching learning is generally known as mobile learning, which includes various educational applications run to smart phones and mobile devices as a tool to learn. Emergence of smart phones in the field of education has brought a great change in the perspective of Information and Communication Technology. It gave a pace to learning as well as e-learning and designs another form of learning generally known as m-learning. Mobile learning is referred to as learning or education via using mobile devices such as smart phones and tablets over the internet or other networks to obtain learning material through different types of educational mobile applications, social interactions and online hubs etc. It has become a need of present time to be competent in mobile technology. During the pandemic CORONA VIRUS (COVID 19), smart phones become played a crucial role in teaching learning process. Teachers taught the students via different online platforms such as **Google Meet, YouTube, WhatsApp, Facebook, Conferencing, Zoom** etc.

In this digital glob, a teacher with his/her old teaching method cannot exist in teaching-learning process. He/she should be skilled in mobile technology to cope with the needs of the present education system. But being skilled in anything, Attitude to concerned object plays a significant role. Attitude is someone's favourable, unfavourable and neutral state to a certain idea, object, people, philosophy, conception, etc. To succeed in a profession, it is imperative that our attitude should be favourable to fulfil the objectives concerned field. Favourable attitude leads to successful

implementation of mobile technology in education process whereas unfavourable attitudes hindrances this process. So, teachers must have favourable attitude to mobile technology to integrate it in education system to achieve the objectives of education.

Objectives

1. To study male and female teachers' attitude to mobile technology.
2. To study married and unmarried teachers' attitude to mobile technology.
3. To study urban and rural teachers' attitude to mobile technology.
4. To study the attitude of teachers of Government/Aided and Self-finance institutions to mobile technology.

Hypotheses

- H1-:** There is significant difference between Attitude of Male and Female teachers to mobile technology.
- H2-:** There is significant difference between Attitude of Married and Unmarried teachers to mobile technology.
- H3-:** There is significant difference between Attitude of Urban and Rural teachers to mobile technology.
- H4-:** There is significant difference between Attitude of teachers of Government/Aide and Self-finance to mobile technology.

Method

Survey Method was used for the current study.

Population

Population of the present study consisted all the teachers, teaching in Higher Education Institutions of District Pilibhit, affiliated to Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

Sample and Sampling

Stratified Random Sampling was used to choose teacher as a sample. Sample consists of 200 teachers (100 male and 100 female) from the population.

Tool

A questionnaire 'Teachers' attitude to usage of mobile technology' was constructed for collection of data.

Statistics

SD, Mean, t-test and p-value was used to analyse data.

Data Processing.

The raw data was processed with (SPSS) version 22.0.

Levels of Significance

Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of Significance.

Analysis of Data

H1-: There is significant difference between Attitude of Male and Female teachers to mobile technology.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Attitude of Male and Female teachers to mobile technology.

Table-1

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Male	100	119.0700	20.71415	2.261	.025	S
Female	100	124.7200	13.97478			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .025 for Attitude to Mobile Technology scores of Male and Female teachers working in Higher Education. Here, p value is less ($p < .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is significant difference between Male and Female teachers' attitude to Mobile Technology. Female teachers had higher attitude as compared to male teachers.

H2-: There is significant difference between Attitude of Married and Unmarried teachers to mobile technology.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Attitude of Married and Unmarried teachers to mobile technology.

Table-2

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Married	100	116.0500	17.45839	4.890	.000	S
Unmarried	100	127.7400	16.33032			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .000 for Attitude to Mobile Technology scores of Married and Unmarried teachers working in Higher Education. Here, p value is less ($p < .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is significant difference between Married and Unmarried teachers' attitude to Mobile Technology. Unmarried teachers had higher attitude as compared to Married teachers.

H3-: There is significant difference between Attitude of Urban and Rural teachers to mobile technology.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Attitude of Urban and Rural teachers to mobile technology.

Table-03

Locality	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Rural	100	122.4800	16.51108	.463	.644	NS
Urban	100	121.3100	19.16209			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .644 for Attitude to Mobile Technology scores of Married and Unmarried teachers working in Higher Education. Here, p value is more ($p > .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban teachers' attitude to Mobile Technology.

H4-: There is significant difference between Attitude of teachers of Government/Aide and Self-finance to mobile technology.

H₀: There is no significant difference between Attitude of teachers of Government/Aide and Self-finance to mobile technology.

Table-04

Type of Management	N	Mean	SD	t-Value	p-Value	S/NS
Government/Aided	100	118.6000	18.93049	2.650	.009	S
SELF-FINANCE	100	125.1900	16.13059			

From the above table, it is evident that the obtain p value is .009 for Attitude to Mobile Technology scores of teachers of Government/Aided and Self-finance teachers working in Higher Education. Here, p value is less ($p < .05$) than .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is significant difference between attitude of teachers of Government/Aided and Self-finance teachers to Mobile Technology. Teachers of self-finance institutions had higher attitude as compared to teachers of government/aided.

Graphical Representation of Analysed Data

Findings

Findings of the study reveal that-

- Female and Male teachers working in higher education institutions differ significantly with respect to Attitude to Mobile Technology. It means there is significant effect of Gender on Attitude to Mobile Technology.
- Unmarried and Married teachers working in higher education institutions differ significantly with respect to Attitude to Mobile Technology. It means there is significant effect of Marital status on Attitude to Mobile Technology.
- Urban and Rural teachers working in higher education institutions did not differ significantly with respect to Attitude to Mobile Technology. It means there is no significant effect of Locality on Attitude to Mobile Technology.
- Teachers of Government/Aided and Self-finance higher education institutions differ significantly with respect to Attitude to Mobile Technology. It means there is significant effect of Type of Management on Attitude to Mobile Technology.

Conclusion

The present study was conducted to find out teachers' attitude to mobile technology. Data was collected and analysed with inferential statistics. Findings of the study revealed that Female teachers, Unmarried teachers, and teachers of Self-finance institutions were more in their attitudes than those of Male teachers, Married teachers and teachers of Government/Aide higher education institutions. As far as effect of Locality was concerned, the study did not find and any significant effect on teachers' attitude to mobile technology. Therefore, this study found no significant effect of locality on teachers' attitudes.

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